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Parametric Optimization Of Flood Prediction Model Based On Synthetic Unit Hydrograph In Meso-Scale Watershed

I Gede Tunas*, Yassir Arafat and Hasanuddin Azikin

Universitas Tadulako, Department of Civil Engineering, Palu, 941 17, Indonesia

*Corresponding author, Email : tunasw@yahoo.com

One of the most important parts of flood risk management is flood forecasting analysis. This analysis plays a role in providing flood potential prediction related to flood mitigation and flood proofing in a vulnerable area. The most commonly used method for estimating flood magnitude especially at ungauged sites is a synthetic unit hydrograph model because of its many advantages, one of which is Snyder. However, the performance of this method depends heavily on the watershed characteristics and generally, the model parameters consisting of storage coefficient (C_p), the coefficient for representing differences in types and locations of the stream (C_t) and constant (n) are difficult to estimate accurately. Consequently, in most cases, this model often produces low performance. This study aims to improve the performance of synthetic unit hydrograph model based on observed hydrologic and hydrometric data in Wuno watershed, one of the mesoscale watersheds which are the part of Palu watershed in central Sulawesi, Indonesia. Surface run-off from Wuno watershed has contributed to the flood that has occurred several times in downstream reach of Palu river. In the initial step of the analysis, the performance of the synthetic unit hydrograph model is evaluated using the Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency coefficient (NSE). If the model tested shows low performance, then it can be improved by performing parameter optimization using QM for Windows. The results of the analysis show that Snyder has low performance in Wuno watershed with NSE number of 0.61. Furthermore, parameter optimization can increase the NSE coefficient to 0.99, where C_p , C_t and n parameters change from 1.1-0.80, 1.0-1.3, 0.25-0.20, respectively. Finally, it can be seen that the optimization procedure is very effective to improve the performance of the synthetic unit hydrograph model.

KEYWORDS

Flood risk management, Hydrology model, Optimization, Tropical river basin

1. INTRODUCTION

Flood forecasting is one of the most important parts of flood disaster management [1]. Indication of flooding is characterized by an abnormal progressive rise in the water level of streams or rivers, which may result in overflowing. Information on the magnitude of flood and its potential impacts can be obtained from flood prediction [2]. This information can be used as a reference to prepare what efforts should be taken to reduce the impact of flooding when the flood disaster really happened. These efforts are part of the flood preparedness in the form of flood prevention and mitigation, flood proofing, warning and evacuation systems [3]. The flood that often occurs in various regions in the world, especially in the tropical area, generally caused by three main factors, namely rainfall, watershed characteristics and anthropogenic factors [4]. The first factor is very natural and difficult to be controlled because it depends on global climate conditions with

very high variability in space and time. The second factor is the assimilation of the watershed nature and management application on the watershed. Watershed management based on land conservation rules can improve the capacity of watersheds to respond to floods. The last factor relates to watershed management, which produced by the influence of human beings on watershed related to land utilization mainly for both agriculture and settlements [5].

Flood prediction as a preliminary analysis of flood mitigation can be done by various methods, one of which is based on synthetic unit hydrograph [6]. This method has been widely used in many regions of the world including Indonesia with various weaknesses and limitations [7]. The advantages of this method are information about flood properties including peak time, peak discharge and base time of flood events can be estimated. In addition, the flood hydrograph curve of a watershed can be used as a reference to determine the watershed properties, mainly land cover of the watershed [5]. One of the most frequently used flood prediction models in Indonesia is Snyder. This method was introduced by Snyder in the United States, based

Figure 1. Location map of research site

on characteristics of watershed geomorphology in the Appalachian mountains [8,9].

This method has been widely used to estimate design floods in various watersheds in Java island, Indonesia especially for the purpose of dam planning. The Jatiluhur dam built in west Java in 1957 and Karangates dam built in east Java in 1977 are two large dams in Indonesia which designed with flood hydrograph based on Snyder model [10]. The two dams are the largest dam built on Java island for irrigation and hydropower purposes. However, from many analytical results that have been obtained, it is indicated that the performance of this model should be evaluated because of the considerable difference between the estimated and observed flood [5]. Based on the results of studies on several measured watersheds in Indonesia as reported by Harto, especially medium and large-sized watersheds proved that the Snyder model showed relatively low performance with a deviation of more than 50% [5]. The study also proved that the parameters of Snyder model especially storage coefficient (C_p) and the coefficient for representing differences in types and locations of the stream (C_r) can be out of ranges as suggested by Snyder [11].

Many researchers have performed optimization parameters of hydrograph model. Kim developed an optimization module for hydrograph analysis using a genetic algorithm in the web GIS-based hydrograph analysis tool (WHAT) [12]. The developed optimization module insignificantly increased the performance of the

hydrograph analysis which measured by Nash Sutcliffe efficiency (NSE) and coefficient of determination (R^2). Kim proposed a methodology to improve the parameter estimation procedure of hydrograph model using hydrograph section separation (HSS) [13]. The optimal parameter can satisfy the objectives of both peak discharge and discharge volume based on the methodology with a good NSE of more than 0.75. Thapa optimized Snyder's synthetic unit hydrograph parameters based on the mean ratio of absolute error (MRAE) in the Karasagala watershed, Sri Lanka with an area of 52.58 km² [14]. Averaged calibrated parameters of the model were in the range of values as suggested by Miller, Hudlow and Thapa [15,16,14]. The recent study was applying the structural procedure of optimization based on NSE as used in QM for Window packages for determining Snyder model parameters in the gauged watershed. The optimal parameters of the model can be used to analyze hydrograph design in other ungauged watersheds particularly especially watersheds having similar properties.

2. MATERIAL AND METHOD

2.1 Study area

Watershed of Wuno with an area of 173.19 km² as the site of this research, administratively situated in Sigi Regency, Province of Central Sulawesi, as illustrated in figure 1. More detailed, it is situated on the geographic coordinates of 119°57'59.10"E - 120°5'27.29"E and 0°55'1.16"S - 1°8'17.80"S. The

River network

Land cover

Figure 2. *Wuno watershed*

watershed is the part of Palu watershed and is consisting of more than three main tributaries which flow water to the main outlet. The topography of the watershed is formed by a large elevation variation and ranges from 80-1700 m above sea level. Generally, it is dominated by a mountainous landscape with a slope of more than 15%, mainly in the middle and upstream of the watershed.

The Wuno watershed has an elongated shape toward the width, with a ratio of 2:1 for the width and length of the watershed. This has an impact on the characteristics of the main river. The length of the main river is relatively very short when compared with the area of the watershed. In addition, the slope of the main river is relatively very steep. The steep land slopes are generally associated with steep channel slopes and conversely [17]. In addition, the slope of the land is associated with stream density, where stream density tends to vary with the land slope [18]. The river network of Wuno watershed is included in medium density. The river network is higher density in upstream and gradually decreases in downstream as the slope declines. The river network is consisting of five order of stream (Figure 2). Basically, most of the land cover of Wuno watershed is primary rain forest with medium to high density. Based on the land cover data obtained from USGS, there is no settlement area in the watershed. It can be seen that only a small part of the area developed as agricultural land mainly in the eastern part of the watershed. The conserved of land cover is expected to maintain and to ensure the supply of

continuous water for drinking and irrigation, mainly for people in Palu valley. There is more than 5000 ha of agriculture land in Palu valley stretched from Gumbasa to Biromaru and Dolo village which get water supply from Palu watershed especially Gumbasa and Wuno Weir.

2.2 Data collection

Data which be used in this research are consisting of a series of rainfall and water level and topographic data. Rainfall and water level data are obtained from hydrology and hydrometric station which installed in Wuno watershed. The gauge stations are managed and operated by river basin management board of Palu-Poso from 2005 until now. However, since 2011 the hydrometric station is no longer working due to the decrease of the river bed at the location of the instrument installation. Recently, the float of water level recorder can not reach the water surface at low discharge. The hydrometric station is mounted approximately 200 m in the upstream of Wuno Weir, precisely on the longitude of 119°57'59.10"E and latitude of 1°1'37.20"S. Both those hydrology and hydrometric stations record hourly data, in the form of hourly rainfall and hourly water level data which can be read graphically. The topographic data is obtained free from the USGS website. The USGS provides many types of topographic data sets, one of them is GTOPO 30 known as SRTM 30, is a near-global digital elevation model (DEM) comprising a combination of data from the shuttle radar topography mission. The usefulness of these data is to derive a digital elevation model (DEM) for gener-

Figure 3. The typical shape of Snyder unit hydrograph

ating stream networks in the whole study area. This DEM is the best resolution data set released by the USGS for free.

2.3 Method

The first step was derived unit hydrograph of the watershed based on a number of pairs of rainfall and flood hydrograph data. Unit hydrograph was obtained by dividing direct runoff hydrograph with the base flow. Secondly, the morphometric analysis was performed to obtained watershed parameters that would be used for determining Snyder unit hydrograph. Watershed parameters were analyzed using GIS based on SRTM data that has been previously downloaded free on the USGS website [19]. Next, the main parameters of Snyder unit hydrograph including time lag (T_L), peak discharge (Q_p) and base time (T_b) can be computed using the following equations:

$$Q_p = 0.278 \left(\frac{C_p}{T_L} \right) \quad \dots(1)$$

$$T_L = C_t (LL_c)^n \quad \dots(2)$$

$$T_p = C_t + \frac{T_r}{2} \quad \dots(3)$$

$$T_b \approx 5T_L \quad \dots(4)$$

Where C_t is storage coefficient (0.73-3.0), C_p is the coefficient for representing differences in types and locations of the stream (0.9-1.4), n is constant, L is main river length (km). L_c is the length of the river from the nearest point of the watershed to the outlet (km). Snyder only prepared an empirical equation for calculating peak discharge and peak time. To obtain the hydrograph ordinate, the calculations are performed using the W50 and W75 approaches as shown in fig-

ure 3. This method has disadvantages associated with the imperfect hydrograph shape and difficulty for obtaining hydrograph ordinates at other points. To overcome the weakness of procedure Alexejev proposed the unit hydrograph equation for improving Snyder equations as follows [10] :

$$Q = f(t) \quad \dots(5)$$

$$Y = \frac{Q}{Q_p}, X = \frac{t}{T_p} \quad \dots(6)$$

$$Y = 10^{-\alpha \frac{(1-X)^2}{X}} \quad \dots(7)$$

$$\alpha = 1.32\lambda^2 + 0.15\lambda + 0.045 \quad \dots(8)$$

$$\lambda = \frac{Q_p T_p}{h A} \quad \dots(9)$$

Where X and Y are hydrograph coordinates and h is rainfall depth of 1 mm. Finally, the performance of Snyder model was evaluated and optimized using Nash Sutcliffe efficiency (NSE) indicator. The indicators were performed using QM for Window packages, expressed as:

$$NSE = 1 - \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (Q_{obs_i} - Q_{sim})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (Q_{obs_i} - \bar{Q}_{obs})^2} \right) \quad \dots(10)$$

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The hourly rainfall in the study area used in this research generally occurs in 2-3 hr duration with different distribution patterns (Figure 4). On a 2 hr duration, maximum rainfall occurs in the first duration and is followed in the second duration. On a 3 hr duration, maximum rainfall occurs in the second duration and is followed by the duration of the third and the first. At the 4 hr duration, a typical hourly rainfall distribution pattern in the study area is closer to the alternating block methods (ABM) distribution pattern. However, in general, this rainfall distribution pattern may vary due to various influences, such as climate change. This distribution pattern is commonly found in various rainfall distribution in Java island and Sumatra island especially Lampung Province, where the highest rainfall percentage occurs at the second hour [20,21]. The trend of this rainfall pattern reflects that the actual hourly rainfall distribution pattern in the research area is not much different from other places in Indonesia, in this case, Java and Sumatra islands, although in general the amount of annual rainfall of each region in Indonesia tends to differ according to meteorological, climatology and geographic location factors that influence it. The pattern of rain distribution plays an important

Figure 4. Average of rainfall intensity in the study area based on the duration

Figure 5. Unit hydrograph of Wuno watershed

role in determining the hydrograph shape of flooding in the river. Furthermore, this rainfall distribution pattern is used as input to derive unit hydrograph on each rainfall discharge pair.

A unit hydrograph is derived from pairs of rainfall and flood hydrograph data by separating base flow based on effective rainfall and phi index (ϕ). Base flow separation is performed using the straight line method with the assumption that the base flow increases with time. Base flow separation techniques in this way have been widely used by hydrological researchers, such as Harto, Limantara and other researchers with various arguments, such as ease in identifying the ending of the base flow on the side of hydrograph recession [22,23,24,25,26]. Unit hydrograph of Wuno watershed is shown in graphical form as in figure 5. It appears that the hydrograph curve has a steep rising side and

recession side with short peak times. This illustrates a typical unit hydrograph of rivers on the island of Sulawesi [27]. This typical shape of hydrograph relates to a steep watershed topography with a short main river length.

Synthetic unit hydrograph derived based on Wuno watershed morphometry characteristics using initial parameters as contained in table 1, has significant differences with measured unit hydrograph (Figure 5). The Snyder model parameters are determined based on the characteristics of the watershed, by accommodating the relationship between the Snyder model parameters with the current characteristics of Wuno watershed. The specified model parameters are in the range of values suggested by Snyder [10,28]. When further observed as shown in figure 5a, differences in the hydrograph curve occur at peak times, peak discharge and base time. The difference of hydrograph basic parameters causes a peak time deviation of 53.17%, peak discharge of 46.27% and a base time of 214%. The magnitude of this deviation is also indicated by a low NSE number of 0.61.

These NSE numbers indicate that the performance of the Snyder model is relatively low in the Wuno watershed. It also illustrates that the selected parameters are essentially incompatible with the characteristics of the relevant watershed [29,30,31]. Determination of several parameters simultaneously is very difficult because of the dependence between parameters. Therefore, optimization of model parameters should be done to improve its performance. The optimization results show that all three parameters change according to the optimization target (Table 1), with excellent NSE numbers (Figure 5b). It also shows that the deviation

Table 1. Parameters of Snyder model

Parameter	C_t	C_p	n	NSE
Before optimization	1.1	1.0	1.25	0.61
After optimization	0.8	1.3	0.20	0.99

of the basic hydrograph parameter decreases drastically below 10%. Optimization results also display that the use of QM for Windows software is very effective for setting optimal parameters.

4. CONCLUSION

The results of the analysis show that Snyder has low performance in Wuno watershed with NSE number of 0.61. Furthermore, parameter optimization can increase the NSE coefficient to 0.99, where C_p , C_t and n parameters change from 1.1-0.80, 1.0-1.3 and 0.25-0.20, respectively. Finally, it can be seen that the optimization procedure is very effective to improve the performance of the synthetic unit hydrograph model.

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